

EHDEN

EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK

806968 – EHDEN

European Health Data & Evidence Network

WP6 – Outreach and Sustainability

D6.3 Analysis of potential Public-Private Partnership exploitation models

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	D6.3 - Analysis of potential Public-Private Partnership exploitation models		
	WP6 – Outreach and Sustainability		Version: v2– Final
	Author(s): Carlos Díaz, Montse Camprubi, Inari Soininen		Security: PU

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DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Description
V0	15 February 2020	First Draft of PPP fiches
V0.1	10 October 2020	PPP fiches available
V1	12 February 2021	First draft of deliverable
V1.01	20 February 2021	Revision
V1.02	12 March 2021	Revised draft
V1.1	20 September 2021	First full draft
V1.2	5 January 2022	Final draft for review
V2	14 January 2022	Final version after consortium review

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the EHDEN Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

EMC	Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam- The Netherlands (Project Coordinator)
Synapse	Synapse Research Management Partners S.L. - Spain
UOXF	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford - United Kingdom
UTARTU	Tartu Ulikool – Estonia
UAVR	Universidade de Aveiro – Portugal
The Hyve	The Hyve BV – the Netherlands
Odysseus	Odysseus Data Services SRO – Czech Republic
EPF	European Patients’ Forum (EPF) – Belgium
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
UMC	Stiftelsen WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring - Sweden
ICHOM	International Consortium for Health Outcomes measurement LTD - United Kingdom
Janssen	Janssen Pharmaceutica NV - Belgium (Project Lead)
Pfizer	Pfizer Limited – United Kingdom
Abbvie	AbbVie Inc - United States
IRIS	Institut De Recherches Internationales Servier – France
SARD	Sanofi Aventis Recherche & Développement – France
Bayer	Bayer Aktiengesellschaft – Germany
Lilly	Eli Lilly and Company Limited – United Kingdom
AZ	AstraZeneca AB – Sweden
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG – Switzerland
UCB	UCB Biopharma SPRL – Belgium
Celgene	Celgene Management SARL – Switzerland
BI	Boehringer Ingelheim International GmbH – Germany

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IMI JU for the undertaking of the EHDEN project (806968).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The EHDEN Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst EHDEN participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties’ obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

This deliverable reports on the study of potential exploitation models relevant to public-private partnerships, analysing previous successful and unsuccessful experiences from other IMI projects and beyond. These will serve as starting points and, potentially, one or more “blueprints” for EHDEN sustainability could be devised to guide initial discussions.

The deliverable includes the methodology used, by creating a template fiche to collect information from project participants, as well as the analysis of the completed fiches, which details the key learnings. Lastly, a summary of considerations is extracted as key for EHDEN’s sustainability.

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1. INTRODUCTION

EHDEN devotes one specific task to Sustainability (task 6.6). This task is centred around designing, innovating, discussing, and deciding about the business models that can secure the long-term sustainability of EHDEN activities. Due to its complex nature and the range of stakeholders involved, EHDEN has the potential to generate value for different types of actors at many different levels, with such value becoming tangible as the project itself progresses.

In the initial phase, this task is focused on the study of potential exploitation models relevant to public-private partnerships, analysing previous successful and unsuccessful experiences from other IMI projects and beyond. These will serve as starting points and, potentially, one or more “blueprints” for EHDEN sustainability could be devised to guide initial discussions.

2. PPP FICHES

To initiate this analysis, WP6 devised template fiches that were subsequently completed by project participants with the information from known initiatives, being those formally Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) or of other types.

The aim of the fiches is to gather basic information from those initiatives, but also to describe more subjective content based on the knowledge and experience from internal members who are also involved in EHDEN. The aim is to collect details from successful initiatives, but also from others that did not perform as expected.

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The basic information collected by each fiche is detailed as follows:

[PPP NAME]

[Website]

Type of initiative	(IMI project, other initiatives, foundation, etc.)
Start and end date	(or ongoing)
Maturity level	(initial, project phase, commercial operation, etc.)
Geographical spread	(national, European, US, worldwide...)
Contact person/s	
EHDEN liaison/contact	
Common partners	

PPP assessment

PPP Summary
QUALIFIERS (short description)
Innovation/competitive advantage:
Cooperation/collaboration/organisation:
Disease focus:
Role of data/databases:
Role of open source/open innovation:
CHARACTERISTICS (sections will be completed according to information available)
Product/service(s):
Who pays for the products/services:
Who provides the products/services:

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Value proposition:

Organisational structure:

(incl. key individuals/backgrounds, governance, management aspects)

Revenue streams:

Costs/budget:

Stakeholders addressed:

(industry, national authorities, academics, healthcare professionals, patients, etc.)

Stakeholders' engagement: (how good they are at communicating with stakeholders –i.e. patient advocates). Impact measures.

Key success factors / limitations: (i.e., success factor: regulatory endorsement)

What can be learnt in terms of sustainability?

What would we like to explore further?

Next steps

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SCORING TABLE	Relevance for EHDEN
Degree of innovation	
Impact	
Feasibility	
Timeliness	
Value proposition	
Organisational structure	
Revenue streams	

Possible scores: N/A, Low, Medium, High

3. LIST AND ASSESSMENT OF PPPs

A first list of initiatives was identified by EHDEN members, who were able to complete the details to be analysed, through having been directly involved or by knowledge within their institutions. The list of initiatives for which a fiche was completed includes the following:

- EU-ADR Alliance
- EMIF
- EHR4CR/I-HD
- CPRD
- Sentinel
- CDISC
- OHDSI
- ODN (has not been evaluated further since it is rather a private – private partnership and thus would not necessarily add value for the EHDEN sustainability topic)
- GetReal Institute

Scoring summary

The fiches included scoring for several aspects that were deemed relevant to potentially extract learnings for EHDEN. To those initially devised in the fiche, three additional criteria were added (science, tools & platforms, standards) for the purposes of this deliverable. These are aimed at better indicating the focus areas of each initiative. Hereunder is the summary of the scoring recorded for the initiatives that were considered most relevant, as judged by WP6 partners:

	EU-ADR Alliance	EMIF	EHR4CR	CPRD	Sentinel	CDISC	OHDSI	GetReal
Degree of innovation	Medium	High	Medium/High	Low	Medium	Medium	High	Medium
Impact	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium	High	High	N/A
Feasibility	High	Medium	Medium	High	Medium	Medium	Low	Medium
Timeliness	Low	Medium	Low	Low	Medium	Medium	High	High
Value proposition	Medium	Low	Medium/High	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium	High
Organisational structure	Medium	N/A	Low	High	Low	High	Low	N/A

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	EU-ADR Alliance	EMIF	EHR4CR	CPRD	Sentinel	CDISC	OHDSI	GetReal
Revenue streams	High	N/A	Medium	High	Low	High	Low	Medium
Science	High	Low	Medium	Medium	High	Low	High	Medium
Tools and Platforms	Medium	Medium	Low	Low	High	Low	High	Low
Standards	Low	Low	Medium	Low	High	High	High	Medium

Summary

<i>High</i>	3	1	1	3	3	4	6	2
<i>Medium</i>	5	4	6	3	5	4	1	5
<i>Low</i>	2	3	3	4	2	2	3	1

These results would indicate that, for each of the different criteria, the top initiatives of reference would be:

Degree of innovation	EMIF, OHDSI, EHR4CR
Impact	CDISC, OHDSI
Feasibility	EU-ADR Alliance, CPRD
Timeliness	OHDSI, GetReal
Value proposition	EHR4CR, GetReal
Organisational structure	CPRD, CDISC
Revenue streams	EU-ADR Alliance, CPRD, CDISC
Science	EU-ADR Alliance, Sentinel, OHDSI
Tools and Platforms	Sentinel, OHDSI
Standards	Sentinel, CDISC, OHDSI

This however doesn't mean that all other initiatives can contribute specific aspects of relevance to one or more criteria, regardless of the given score.

4. PPP FICHES ANALYSIS

The aim of this deliverable is to analyse existing public and private partnerships (PPP) in order to learn from experiences that could inform EHDEN sustainability strategies. The analysis of these PPPs contributes to the creation of a repository of collective knowledge that can be used to develop future scenarios for EHDEN. In group discussions held, it was clear that the learnings could be obtained either from successful initiatives, but also from other initiatives which were unsuccessful in the end. For this reason, the input received in each of the fiches not only collected factual information about the PPPs, but also subjective views from EHDEN partners that had insights into specific PPPs; thus, posing some limitations to the exercise due to potential bias. These subjective views are not included in this deliverable for reasons of confidentiality .

The list of initiatives analysed was based on the knowledge from EHDEN members, as pointed above, and it comprises not only past IMI projects, but also other initiatives that were deemed relevant for EHDEN. This widens the scope at all levels: the product or service offered, the organisational structure, the value proposition prepared, etc., well beyond archetypes most commonly found in IMI projects. However, this heterogeneity also introduces some difficulties in doing a direct comparison with EHDEN and the subsequent lessons that can be applied, as the IMI funding scheme has specific characteristics and derived rules that affect, for example, intellectual property or access rights.

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EHDEN itself already contains several activities that can be an objective for sustainability independently, e.g., SME certification, Data Partner onboarding, tool/method development, the Academy, etc. Each of these “products/services” could be developed into potential businesses by themselves, and combined solutions could be devised, too. Each of these possibilities have to be considered on its own merits as part of sustainability studies.

Key learnings

Innovation/competitive advantage:

Standardisation and federated networks are key themes in most of the initiatives analysed. However, there are other initiatives that rely on allowing industry and other stakeholders to access/purchase data directly, which simplifies the value proposition. By design, this is not a possibility considered in EHDEN.

Regarding standardisation, an important point to be considered for its application and widespread adoption is to be required for regulatory purposes. This is the example of CDISC, which started as a volunteer approach, and is currently the standard required by a variety of regulatory bodies across the globe (e.g. FDA, NMPA, PMDA) for submission of clinical trial data for regulatory submissions and approvals. Recently, regulatory agencies have consistently relayed the importance of a common data model, which represents a significant opportunity for OMOP in the regulatory space – this is exemplified by the recent DARWIN call launched by the EMA, a key initiative for the future of observational studies for regulatory purposes in Europe, and which explicitly demands the use of a common data model as cornerstone for high-throughput study execution strategies. However, regulators are generally known to be risk-averse in terms of innovations, with quite some heterogeneity and fragmentation observed across European countries, so a space for progressive uptake such as the one that could be provided by EHDEN may be ideal to incentivise regulatory buy-in. Here, the close relationship of EHDEN with OHDSI is a relevant asset.

Additionally, the ‘honest broker’ concept was introduced as an innovation by the EU-ADR Alliance, as means of a single interface towards the customer which streamlines the procedures and helps to reduce the overhead of liaising with several data sources for a single study. Although CROs could be seen to play a similar role, the federated nature of the EU-ADR Alliance (hence, enhanced autonomy of data sources) is a key differentiator.

Both EMIF, EHR4CR and OHDSI rank high in terms of innovation, being predecessors of EHDEN in terms of federated data networks for observational studies and fostering of the use of the OMOP CDM, respectively. OHDSI has been especially productive in terms of innovating tools and methods and testing them through use cases and non-commercial studies and has grown enormously in terms of constituency over the last few years. EHDEN has successfully innovated a formal process for Data Partner onboarding that can represent additional value.

Cooperation/collaboration/organisation:

The organisational approaches used in the initiatives analysed are quite varied. We have examples ranging from open community to the creation of a foundation or institute, with structures that lie somewhere in between, such as having a Coordination Centre, or the honest broker concept discussed above. Memberships led by an executive team have also been used as a way of organisation, priming certain key organisations as leaders that can operationally drive the initiative.

Some initiatives like the EU-ADR Alliance could be seen more as loosely connected networks of data providers with one party acting as interface – without a formally established “institution” underpinning it. The case of OHDSI is even more extreme, as it is a completely open, volunteer-based network of interested researchers. This approach maximises flexibility, but it may hamper some business opportunities. Other initiatives have

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taken the opposite approach and rely on an institution of some sort (e.g., the recently established GetReal Institute) to front the initiative, regardless of the many collaborators that may be behind it. There seems to be a psychological effect in having a standing institution in terms of creating reassurance in the market and conveying the adequate perception. This effect may be somewhat diluted if the institution is newly created (and, therefore, lacks a track record and/or capacity). Creating an institution takes time and funding to set up and grow, and it may be less flexible than a pure network of interested parties united by a common vision, procedures and incentives.

It is also clear that internal buy-in of any sustainability solution is as important as external buy-in. Getting consensus within the project across participating institutions needs to be balanced with creating something of value for external stakeholders, that can favourably compare to existing solutions in one or more dimensions. Neglecting internal buy-in can undermine support in the critical first stages and hamper the creation of adequate capacity to launch a sustainable initiative. Neglecting external buy-in may lead to an initiative that is perfectly consensual, but lacks attractiveness to potential customers and stakeholders. Value propositions need to consider this dual dimension, to avoid some of the shortcomings observed in previous PPPs.

Role of data/databases:

Regarding the role of the data or the databases associated with each of the initiatives, we also find different approaches. The creation of a network is a common aspect in most of these initiatives, which is also at the core of EHDEN project with the creation of a federated structure of Data Partners and SMEs.

The relation with databases and access to the several databases within each network is different across these initiatives. Whereas in some cases we see that the network is formed by data custodians, some of those related to IMI projects were not able to go beyond the relationships established among the consortium members within the funding period. We also have an example of a totally open network structure, with members from multiple databases of different types that can take part in any study. Incentives for data custodians are key in any case, while providing a structure that allows for adherence to the respective local rules and regulations, including ethics approvals.

Another perspective is provided by the EU-ADR Alliance, in which data sources freely join the initiative for the use of the data itself with the aim of performing studies together. In that particular case, legal relationships are bespoke and circumscribed to the execution of each study.

As a valuable learning for EHDEN, we discovered that one of the projects analysed had data custodians as partners in the consortium who were mapping to the OMOP CDM. However, at the end of the project those Data Partners remained separated. EHDEN is working hard to prevent this case scenario by creating a strong sustainable community of Data Partners to endure beyond the project phase, but the risk of disengagement when funding becomes more uncertain cannot be discounted. The EHDEN project team is, however, working on solutions to prevent a collapse of the project ecosystem after the IMI project phase from happening.

Role of open source/open innovation:

Overall, the initiatives analysed are often based on open-source technologies and open innovation approaches. OHDSI, for instance, is at the forefront in terms of open-source approaches, as it gathers collaborators in an open manner to collaboratively develop and evolve a number of open-source standards, methods and tools, which are also widely used in many other projects or initiatives beyond the ones herein analysed. It emphasizes the community concept; however, some stakeholders may be reluctant to conduct important studies owing to doubts in terms of reliable performance and timeliness of results according to

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commercial standards. Here, relative specialisation in certain studies or data exploitation exercises may be important to occupy a specific ‘market niche’.

The “free” collaboration scheme, totally in line with open innovation, is another common aspect shared by some of the initiatives. The EU-ADR Alliance is a clear example using this model of collaboration with no explicit hierarchy, granting plenty of flexibility and autonomy to the partners involved, and where legal arrangements are only set up *ad hoc* when strictly necessary. However, the membership is quite restricted and requires unanimity of existing members to accept a new one.

Revenue streams

Beyond project funding, the sources of revenue in the initiatives analysed can be summarised as follows:

- Membership fees
- Licensing fees
- Study/research services
- Database analyses services
- Governmental funding/grants
- Consulting fees

Stakeholders addressed:

Across all the initiatives, the variety of stakeholders addressed includes:

- Academia
- Pharmaceutical companies
- Contract Research Organisations
- Regulatory, HTA and governmental agencies
- Technology/software developers
- Healthcare institutions and professionals
- Funding agencies/other stakeholders (e.g., philanthropic organisations)
- Patient organisations
- Insurance companies

What can we learn in terms of sustainability

The study of the previous and existing PPPs is central to the preparatory work for the EHDEN project sustainability plan. There are many lessons that can be learned from previous initiatives, such as the models used in each case and their success/failure, as well as possibilities for improvement. Each initiative is determined by its origin, objectives, constituency and applicable legal framework, which are all very varied. Considering the characteristics and wide scope of EHDEN, plus its potential for expansion in several areas, it is safe to conclude that no single initiative offers a complete ‘blueprint’ that can be directly applied to EHDEN.

Initiating sustainability discussions and devising scenarios early on in the project is of utmost importance, as this significantly helps to secure the required support to achieve sustainability before the end of the grant agreement period. This is clearly perceived from some of the initiatives analysed, translating into one of the key learnings. Any sustainability effort requires time both to achieve initial consensus within the consortium and for subsequent actions to turn the approved plans into something tangible. Time is also a key factor when reaching out to potential funders, as decisions require the participation of several functions within an institution. In the case of EHDEN, the international environment related to evidence generation using real-

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world data is moving very rapidly, with companies, projects and political priorities developing at an accelerated pace.

Another aspect to be considered is the possibility to build on a modular approach which can create a variety of routes towards sustainability. This strategy relies on separately considering the different products/services that can result because of the project, assuming there may be different exploitation models (structure, organisation, revenue streams, etc.) applying to each.

The “free” collaboration paradigm explained in the previous section could also arise within the EHDEN ecosystem in due time, for instance, with a number of “alliances” among data partners that may spontaneously develop.

Another concept highlighted in the analysis as one of the key success factors is the availability of a strong leadership at the beginning of the sustainability effort that can drive all the necessary actions towards sustainable operations without endless discussions.

Experience also shows that not all planned scenarios at the beginning of a sustainability exercise might be successful. For this reason, it will be important to work on several alternatives and scenarios that can lead to different paths along the process.

As a summary, the following considerations are regarded as key for EHDEN’s sustainability:

- Support/endorsement of regulatory and governmental agencies in terms of promotion and use of a common data model would be a booster to the EHDEN ecosystem.
- Move from a ‘project sustainability’ to an ‘asset sustainability’ perspective is necessary to account for the project’s richness.
- Honest appraisal of the different assets resulting from the project in terms of their potential for sustainable operation is of critical importance, while keeping a coherent overall mission that provides a common framework.
- A variety of funding sources need to be considered, from research grants to privately funded observational studies, which may be applicable to different assets.
- The organisational structure should be flexible to adapt to changing demands and uncertainties in the context of a rapidly-moving international environment.
- Timeliness is key to benefit from windows of opportunity. This may require initiating sustainable operations of certain assets well before the end of the project phase.
- Internal buy-in from project partners needs to be balanced with external stakeholders buy-in.
- Relationships with Data Partners and SMEs in the ecosystem are critically important to define, from onboarding to operations, on several levels (motivational, organisational, legal, financial, technical, etc.).

5. NEXT STEPS

After the analysis, EHDEN is working on the preparation of the first scenarios towards the sustainability work.

The efforts will be reported in the next deliverable D6.4 First version of sustainability, with consecutive annual deliverables reporting on the progress towards achieving the best approach possible for EHDEN sustainability.

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ANNEX 1. PPP SUMMARY

EU-ADR Alliance (<http://eu-adr-alliance.com/>)

Type of initiative	FP7 project-derived
Start and end date	2012 - ongoing
Maturity level	Commercial operations
Geographical spread	European
Contact person/s	Johan van der Lei (EMC)
EHDEN liaison/contact	Johan van der Lei, Peter Rijnbeek (EMC)
EHDEN common partners	EMC, SYNAPSE

PPP Summary

The EU-ADR Alliance builds on the results of the European project “EU-ADR: Exploring and Understanding Adverse Drug Reactions by Integrative Mining of Clinical Records and Biomedical Knowledge” (funded by the ICT Unit of the European Commission within the 7th Framework Programme (FP7)), which intended to be a breakthrough in the use of technology to improve pharmacovigilance in federated studies.

The EU-ADR Alliance was devised as a collaboration framework for running studies and answering drug safety questions in a federated manner, using extracted data from multiple European EHR and healthcare databases. For this, it leverages the tools and methods developed in the framework of the EU-ADR project. The EU-ADR Alliance is composed of members bringing in relevant expertise (EHR databases, information technologies, epidemiological research). It is based on the concept of federated databases, non-competition with its members, independence, and scientific interest. The EU-ADR Alliance provides a framework to set up and run more powerful studies faster, by virtue of pre-arranged governance and operating methods, which allow to streamline procedures and accelerate study implementation.

EMIF (<http://emif.eu>)

Type of initiative	IMI1
Start and end date	2013 - 2018
Maturity level	Completed
Geographical spread	European
Contact person/s	Johan van der Lei (EMC)
EHDEN liaison/contact	Johan van der Lei, Peter Rijnbeek (EMC), Nigel Hughes (JANSSEN)
EHDEN common partners	EMC, SYNAPSE, JANSSEN, TARTU, SANOFI, SERVIER, UCB

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PPP Summary

EMIF was initiated to create a technology and governance framework for the identification, assessment, access, and reuse of health data for real world research (pre-empting FAIR principles). The project was three-in-one, the technology and governance framework, EMIF-PLAT, and two validating disease-foci projects for early biomarker development, in the metabolic consequences of obesity, EMIF-MET, and in Alzheimer’s Disease (EMIF-AD). Originally, EMIF was to have further disease-foci projects added, but this did not proceed. EMIF was a challenging project with 57 partners in 14 countries, and importantly Data Partners (~14) were inside the Consortium. The project was probably ahead of its time at its inception and struggled initially to overcome challenges related to working with data, and technical approaches. OMOP CDM was utilised halfway through the project, and ~10 Data Partner’s databases were mapped to varying degrees, with initial work within the OHDSI framework presaging EHDEN. EMIF was influential and important in setting the stage for EHDEN, especially with regard to increasing receptiveness to federated networks. It did not achieve full evaluation of the platform, and EMIF-AD engaged, whereas EMIF-MET did not with EMIF-PLAT. Sustainability was discussed considerably in the last third of the project, but only resulted in a potential spinoff of EMIF-AD (still ongoing), and the platform remains hosted at University of Aveiro. The EMIF-PLAT platform created a Data Source Catalogue with metadata fingerprints (utilised within EHDEN), and a mixture of tools for EHR and cohort-derived data.

EHR4CR (<http://www.ehr4cr.eu/>)

Type of initiative	IMI 1 project
Start and end date	2011 – 2016
Maturity level	Completed in the InSite platform and in production in Europe, sold to TriNetX (April 2019) – now
Geographical spread	European
Contact person/s	Mats Sundgren (AZ)
EHDEN liaison/contact	Mats Sundgren (AZ), Johann Proeve (Bayer)
EHDEN common partners	None

PPP Summary

The IMI EHR4CR project ran between 2011 and 2016 with a budget of +16 million € and involved 34 partners (academic and industrial) and two subcontractors. It was funded by the Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI) and the European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations (EFPIA). EHR4CR was one of the largest public-private partnerships aiming at providing adaptable, reusable, and scalable solutions (tools and services) for reusing data from Electronic Health Record systems for Clinical Research. Electronic Health Record (EHR) data offer large opportunities for the advancement of medical research, the improvement of healthcare, and the enhancement of patient safety (<http://www.ehr4cr.eu>)

The project was focused on developing scalable services towards four different scenarios, i.e., protocol feasibility, site and patient identification, clinical trial conduct and safety analyses. Data were supposed to be re-used/accessed via a federated network of data providers, such as university clinics and hospitals. Data mapping was planned to be done by the data sources and could be used by the participating partners on the project during the project period.

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CPRD (<https://www.cprd.com/public>)

Type of initiative	Non-profit government research service
Start and end date	Ongoing (more than 30 years)
Maturity level	Full matured infrastructure delivering services
Geographical spread	United Kingdom (national)
Contact person/s	
EHDEN liaison/contact	Daniel Prieto Alhambra
EHDEN common partners	Oxford, Lilly

PPP Summary

“Clinical Practice Research Datalink (CPRD) is a real-world research service supporting retrospective and prospective public health and clinical studies. CPRD is jointly sponsored by the Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency and the National Institute for Health Research (NIHR), as part of the Department of Health and Social Care in the UK.

CPRD collects de-identified patient data from a network of GP practices across the UK. Primary care data are linked to a range of other health related data to provide a longitudinal, representative UK population health dataset. The data encompass 42 million patient lives, including 13 million currently registered patients. For more than 30 years, research using CPRD data and services has informed clinical guidance and best practice, resulting in over 2,300 peer-reviewed publications investigating drug safety, use of medicines, effectiveness of health policy, health care delivery and disease risk factors.”

(Source: CPRD public website - <https://www.cprd.com/home>)

CPRD comprises currently of two different data sources, based on information recorded from two different primary care EMR software: CPRD GOLD based on VisionTM and CPRD AURUM based on EmisTM.

Sentinel (<https://www.sentinelinitiative.org/>)

Type of initiative	Regulatory Agency federated network
Start and end date	Pre-phase pilot “mini-Sentinel”: 2008 – 2016 Sentinel System: 2016 – ongoing
Maturity level	Mature phase
Geographical spread	US
Contact person/s	Richard Platt (Principal Investigator of the Sentinel program)
EHDEN liaison/contact	None
EHDEN common partners	None

	D6.3 - Analysis of potential Public-Private Partnership exploitation models		
	WP6 – Outreach and Sustainability	Version: v2– Final	
	Author(s): Carlos Díaz, Montse Camprubi, Inari Soininen	Security: PU	18/20

Summary

The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) Sentinel Initiative originated from a legislative mandate to develop a safety surveillance system. A pilot programme designed to assess potential drug safety signals in insurance claims was launched in 2008. Fully implemented in 2016, the Sentinel System is now a core feature of FDA’s post-market safety surveillance armamentarium. Using its multi-site, privacy-preserving, curated data infrastructure and suite of analysis tools, Sentinel now proactively monitors medical product safety from insurance claims, registries, and Electronic Health Records (EHR).

CDISC (<https://www.cdisc.org/>)

Type of initiative	Non-profit government research service
1997	1997 – ongoing
Maturity level	Full matured infrastructure delivering standards, technology
Geographical spread	International
Contact person/s	N/A
EHDEN liaison/contact	N/A
EHDEN common partners	All biopharma EHDEN members

PPP Summary

CDISC began as an all-volunteer organisation in 1997 with no funding. After developing two draft standards and a glossary, CDISC was incorporated as a non-profit organisation in February 2000 and Dr. Kush (President and CEO of CDISC) raised initial funding of \$500,000 from contributions by 32 charter member organisations and hired the first CDISC employee. Over the next two decades, CDISC grew to over 400 member organizations, an annual revenue of \$7.5 million from diverse sources, and thousands of volunteers. Under the leadership of Dr. Kush, CDISC standards gained the respect of researchers, government entities and patient-centered groups worldwide. The CDISC volunteer-driven and consensus-based standards development process was recognised by ISO and resulted in a suite of CDISC foundational clinical research standards (supporting protocol through analysis and reporting) with extensions specific for therapeutic areas relevant to the health of billions of people worldwide. Additional achievements included the requirement of CDISC standards by regulators in the U.S. (FDA) and Japan (PMDA); the European Medicines Agency (EMA) linking CDISC standards to their requirements for clinical trial applications; the CDISC Europe Foundation formed to work with the Innovative Medicines Initiative; the BRIDG model to bridge healthcare and research as a CDISC, HL7 and ISO standard with FDA and NCI as key stakeholders; and the launch of the Healthcare Link Initiative and CDISC Shared Health and Research Electronic Library (SHARE). – Source: <https://www.cdisc.org/about/president-emeritus>

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OHDSI (<https://ohdsi.org/>)

Type of initiative	The Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) community OHDSI is NOT a formal organisation but rather a community of people from participating organisations
Start and end date	Ongoing
Maturity level	Emerging
Geographical spread	Worldwide with multiple regional chapters (US, EU, China, South Korea and Japan)
Contact person/s	Patrick Ryan
EHDEN liaison/contact	Peter Rijnbeek
Common partners	EMC, Odysseus, The Hyve, Janssen

PPP Summary

The Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (or OHDSI, pronounced "Odyssey") programme is a multi-stakeholder, interdisciplinary collaborative to bring out the value of health data through large-scale analytics. All its solutions are open-source. The OHDSI research community enables active engagement across multiple disciplines (e.g., clinical medicine, biostatistics, computer science, epidemiology, life sciences) and spans multiple stakeholder groups (e.g., researchers, patients, providers, payers, product manufacturers, regulators).

OHDSI is a worldwide community with multiple region/country specific chapters that were formed. The coordinating institutions for the OHDSI US chapter is Columbia University and Medical Center (Dr. George Hripcsak). The EU Chapter is coordinated by EMC (Dr. Peter Rijnbeek) and University of Oxford (Dr. Daniel Prieto Alhambra) and South Korean OHDSI Chapter is coordinated by Ajou University (Dr. Ray Park).

OHDSI has established an international network of researchers and observational health databases.

- 2,500 distinct users across six continents have posted to OHDSI community forum
- > 100 different databases
- > 500 million patient records
- Data from 19 different countries, with > 200 million patient records from outside the U.S.

Oncology Data Network (ODN)

Type of initiative	A private-private partnership. The first multi-country European collaboration of its kind revealing how anti-cancer medicines are being used at scale in near real-time
Start and end date	Started in late 2017 and still ongoing
Maturity level	(Initial, project phase, commercial operation, etc)
Geographical spread	Europe: England, France and Spain
Contact person/s	
EHDEN liaison/contact	

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Common partners

PPP Summary

The ODN was a private-private partnership. It required a very large investment upfront to create a GDPR-compliant system, much of which was apparently completed. It emphasised speed and breadth over depth – information was available from about one week earlier, but only a small number of variables. The main incentive for hospitals was apparently gaining access to tools in addition to their own data for their own research purposes.

GetReal Institute (<https://www.getreal-institute.org/>)

Type of initiative	The GetReal Institute drives best practices in the adoption of RWE in health care decision-making in Europe. A non-profit member-led organisation, building on Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI) projects GetReal and GetReal Initiative.
Start and end date	Started April 2021, ongoing
Maturity level	Emerging
Geographical spread	Europe, with global ambition
Contact person/s	Pieter Stolk
EHDEN liaison/contact	NICE
Common partners	NICE, Janssen and other pharma companies-

PPP Summary

The GetReal Institute builds on the success of two IMI projects: GetReal and The GetReal Initiative, and brings together a wide variety of stakeholders to drive the sustainable development and adoption of tools, methods, and best practices in the generation and use of RWE for better health care decision-making.

The GetReal Institute is:

- A Platform to reach common understanding and prioritisation of critical opportunities and challenges in the generation and use of RWE
- An Incubator and “design lab” for strategies and tools to clarify scientific and operational uncertainties in RWE approaches and methods
- A Source of trusted, high quality RWE education and training resources
- A Hub for connecting RWE-related initiatives within Europe and beyond